

KINETICS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN FORMALDEHYDE AND AMMONIA

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The formation of hexamethylenetetramine has been studied in aqueous solutions at two different temperatures by mixing stoichiometric proportions of H.CHO and NH_4OH , and determining the rate of disappearance of the aldehyde. The reaction has been found to be a third-order one. The presence of an intermediate complex has been detected, which on hydrolysing with dilute acetic acid yields H.CHO and NH_4OH in equimolecular proportions. A three-step mechanism has been proposed involving a Mannich type of reaction.

Baur and Ruetchi (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1941, 24, 754) studied the kinetics of this reaction by titrating ammonium hydroxide with the acid in presence of phenol red. They could not draw any definite conclusion, but indicated the probability of a third order reaction. It is felt that the reaction is a fast one, hence it becomes imperative that it should first be arrested and then the constituents estimated. Boyd and Winkler (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1947, 25B, 387) studied this reaction from 0° to 35° and obtained three rate curves based on ammonia consumed, formaldehyde consumed and tetramine formed. The curves, specially at higher temperatures, were widely separated and so the order of the reaction could not be evaluated. In view of this uncertainty, a study of its kinetics was undertaken after having arrived at a new iodometric method of estimating formaldehyde in presence of ammonium salts and tetramine. The procedure is a modification of Romijn's hypiodite method (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1897, 36, 19).

EXPERIMENTAL

Method of Evaluating Formaldehyde.—Romijn's method cannot be used in presence of ammonium salts as the reaction is carried out in the alkaline medium and the NH_4OH formed combines with I_2 . It was observed that on adding a solution containing 3% HgCl_2 and about 40% KI, the interference caused by NH_4OH was completely prevented. The ammonium probably forms a soluble complex with K_2HgI_4 in presence of a large excess of KI. Synthetic mixtures of H.CHO (0.075M) and NH_4Cl (0.05M) were extensively analysed by this method, affording satisfactory results within 0.5% error (this *Journal*, 1957, 35, 497). It has already been claimed by Dorrer and Ozimic (*Farm. Glasnik*, 1949, 5, No. 9/10, 174) that tetramine does not interfere with Romijn's method.

The reaction mixture (5-10 c.c.) after freezing in 0.1 N acetic acid was pipetted out into a 100 c.c. conical flask and treated with a freshly prepared HgCl_2 -KI solution (8 c.c.). After adding 0.1 N I_2 (10 c.c., by pipette) and 1.0N-NaOH (2 c.c.), the flask was corked and left for 20 minutes at about 20°. The contents were then acidified with 1.0N-HCl (4 c.c.), and the I_2 liberated was titrated with 0.05 N hypo solution to

starch end-point. A blank was carried out, similar in all respects except for the addition of the H.CHO mixture. The difference in the hypo readings gave the amount of I_2 consumed by H.CHO during its oxidation.

Arresting the Reaction.—The reaction being a comparatively fast one, care was taken in recording time precisely with a stop-watch. A mixture of NH_4OH and H.CHO stops reacting when acidified, but if a mineral acid is used, the tetramine formed hydrolyses to H.CHO and NH_4OH . A dilute solution of acetic acid was found more suitable as it had a negligible effect on tetramine. The reaction was started in every case by adding the H.CHO solution from a fast pipette to a solution of NH_4OH and it was arrested by taking a definite volume of this mixture in a pipette and adding to an equal volume of 0.1 N acetic acid. The pipette used had a delivery time of 6 seconds. The acidified reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 20 minutes so as to decompose the intermediate complex and then an aliquot (5 to 10 c.c.) was pipetted out for evaluating H.CHO taking part in the formation of tetramine only.

The Order of the Reaction

(a). *By Half-life Method.*—An attempt was made to evaluate the order from the measurements of "half-life", by finding out the time required for the disappearance of half of the H.CHO, when mixed with a stoichiometric proportion of NH_4OH .

For a third order reaction, if the three reactants are in equal concentrations,

$$K_3 = \frac{1}{2t} \left\{ \frac{1}{(a-x)^3} - \frac{1}{a^3} \right\}$$

if $\frac{1}{2}a$ is substituted for x ,

$$t_{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{3}{2k_3 a^2}.$$

For two initial concentrations of A and a , if "half-lives" are $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ then

$$\frac{t_{\frac{1}{2}}}{T_{\frac{1}{2}}} = \frac{A^2}{a^2}.$$

The above expression has been applied to various initial concentrations of H.CHO and the "half-life" calculated. The results are recorded in Table I. The experimental and the calculated values are in fair agreement, showing that the contention of a third order reaction is correct.

TABLE I

Initial conc.		Half-life at 20°.		Half-life at 15°.	
H.CHO.	NH_4OH .	Exp.	Calc.	Exp.	Calc.
0.15 M	0.10 M	6.0 min.	...	10.0 min.	...
0.10	0.067	13.5	13.5 min.	22.0	22.5 min.
0.075	0.05	23.0	24.0	38.5	40.0
0.06	0.04	36.5	37.5	61.0	62.5

(b). *By Plotting $1/C^2$ against Time.*—In a third order reaction $t \propto 1/C^2$, if the three reactants are in equal concentrations. In this case there are only two reactants, which, when present in stoichiometric proportions, yield a straight line (Fig. 1) on

plotting t against $1/C^2$, where C is the concentration of H.CHO. The reactions were followed to about 78% of completion.

Intermediate Complex.—The reaction mixture containing H.CHO and NH₄OH, when acidified with dilute acetic acid, was found to contain an intermediate complex, which hydrolysed much more rapidly than tetramine. A study of the hydrolysis of 0.01 *M* tetramine solution by 0.05 *N* acetic acid at 20° revealed that it was a very slow process. It can be neglected when the two reactants come in contact for 20 to 30 minutes only. The intermediate complex, on the other hand, hydrolysed very rapidly and in 30 minute's time broke up completely into H.CHO and NH₄OH. Its hydrolysis was studied by mixing equal volumes of 0.15 *M*-HCHO and 0.1 *M*-NH₄OH and allowing the reaction to proceed to half completion and then it was arrested by pouring in an equal volume of ice-cold 0.1 *N* acetic acid. This acidified solution (10 c.c.) was immediately withdrawn for the estimation of H.CHO. The rest of the solution was kept at 20° and 10 c.c. pipetted out at various time intervals for evaluating H.CHO. The results, as recorded in Table II, show that the H.CHO content of the solution rapidly increases in the initial stages and attains a stable value after 30 minutes when the decomposition of the complex is complete.

TABLE II

Time.	Total H.CHO obtained (c.c. of 0.025 M soln.)	H.CHO obtained by hydrolysis of the complex (c.c. of 0.025 M soln.).
0 min.	6.15	...
5	7.30	1.15
10	7.80	1.65
15	8.00	1.85
30	8.25	2.10
45	8.20	2.05
60	8.25	2.10

The intermediate complex on hydrolysis also produced NH_4OH which, when estimated by titrating the acidified mixture with NaOH in presence of phenol red, was found to be in equimolecular proportion with H.CHO . Experiments were repeated several times to confirm this.

DISCUSSION

Polly *et al.* (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1947, **25B**, 525), who studied the action of ammonium salts on H.CHO from p_x 4 to 8, also postulated the formation of a byproduct because more NH_3 and H.CHO were consumed than could be accounted for by the formation of tetramine. Richmond *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3659) put forward the view that $\text{HN}-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}-\text{CH}_2$ was produced as an intermediate com-

plex. The present worker holds that there is an undeniable evidence in favour of the existence of an intermediate complex which is unstable in presence of dilute acetic acid and decomposes completely into equimolecular proportions of H.CHO and NH_3 . The complex which undergoes such a rapid hydrolysis is probably a simpler compound like $\text{CH}_3=\text{NH}$ or $\text{CH.OH}-\text{NH}_2$.

The probable mechanism of the reaction is :

[Complex A]

[Complex B]

No evidence can be adduced in support of the first step except for the detection of the intermediate complex. It is probably an instantaneous reaction which soon comes to an equilibrium. The second step is a Mannich type of reaction ; here the same molecule is the base and the active hydrogen compound. This reaction is a slow one and accounts for the disappearance of H.CHO in accordance with a third order reaction,

as already established. In the third step the complex B polymerises to furnish a more stable structure consisting of 3 interlocked hexagons, in the manner shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

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